

Teachers' and Parents' Lived Experiences with Academic Challenges and Student Success in Cambodian Primary Schools: A Qualitative Study in Pailin Province

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Abstract

Improving educational quality remains a critical challenge in Cambodia, particularly in primary education, where many students continue to struggle with foundational literacy and numeracy skills. In response, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport introduced the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) to strengthen teaching quality, school leadership, accountability, and community participation across public primary schools. However, few empirical studies have examined how these standards are experienced by teachers and parents at the school level. This qualitative study explores teachers' and parents' lived experiences with academic challenges and student success in Cambodian primary schools in Pailin Province. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions with 52 participants, including school principals, teachers, parents, and members of school management committees from five primary schools. The data were analyzed via thematic analysis. The findings reveal that academic challenges are shaped by interconnected structural, institutional, and family-level factors, including student health and learning difficulties, family poverty, limited parental education, heavy teacher workload, insufficient instructional resources, and inconsistent community engagement. Moreover, student success was associated with regular attendance, teacher encouragement, parental monitoring, effective home-school communication, and collaborative stakeholder support. The study highlights the importance of strengthening teacher support, leadership capacity, and inclusive, context-sensitive parental engagement to enhance the implementation of MPSS. These findings contribute context-specific qualitative insights into education reform in Cambodia and offer practical implications for policymakers, school leaders, and educators seeking to improve learning outcomes in resource-constrained settings.

Keywords: *Teachers' lived experiences, parental involvement, academic challenges, academic success, Cambodian primary education, MPSS.*

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Introduction

Education is a fundamental pillar of human capital development and a prerequisite for national progress and global sustainability. Recognizing that educational quality must be nurtured from the

earliest stages of child development, primary education is particularly significant, as it builds essential literacy, numeracy, ethical, and behavioral competencies that form the foundation for lifelong learning. In this context, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports has introduced a model primary school standard to serve as a benchmark for autonomous and accountable school management, guiding stakeholders across the sector. This initiative prioritizes the strengthening of foundational reading and mathematics instruction in Grade 1 and aligns with the broader policy objective of ensuring equitable access to inclusive, high-quality education for all Cambodians. Recent sector data reflect steady progress toward these goals. During the reporting period, Cambodia recorded 7,398 public and 890 private primary schools serving a total of 2,261,216 students. Although overall primary enrollment declined slightly by 4,567 students, the Grade 1 net admission rate rose sharply to 97.25%, indicating a return to prepandemic enrollment levels after the substantial disruption caused by COVID-19. Moreover, teacher deployment strategies are being refined: a policy-driven reduction in dual-class and combined-class teaching has been accompanied by the recruitment of an additional 622 contract teachers, with the aim of improving instructional quality and optimizing the allocation of human resources (Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport, 2025).

Improving educational quality remains one of the most pressing challenges in global development, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Although access to primary schooling has expanded substantially, many children have completed several years of education without acquiring foundational literacy and numeracy skills (Akyeampong & Fofack, 2019; World Bank, 2018; Sam et al., 2025). This global learning crisis has shifted policy attention away from enrollment alone toward the quality of teaching, school leadership, and system accountability (UNESCO, 2022). Cambodia has made notable progress in expanding access to primary education and achieving near-gender parity. Nevertheless, concerns about learning quality persist, particularly in the Khmer language and mathematics, with students in rural areas facing disproportionate disadvantages (Benveniste et al., 2008; MoEYS, 2023; UNESCO, 2022; Sam et al., 2025). These challenges threaten national efforts to strengthen human capital, reduce poverty, and promote social equity.

In response, the Royal Government of Cambodia prioritized education reform under the Pentagonal Strategy–Phase I (Royal Government of Cambodia, 2023), including the introduction of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport (MoEYS, 2023; Sam et al., 2025). The MPSS framework aims to improve instructional quality, strengthen school leadership, enhance accountability, and promote community participation. Despite its policy significance, limited empirical research has examined how MPSS is experienced by teachers and parents or how it shapes everyday teaching and learning practices at the school level. This study addresses this gap by exploring teachers’ and parents’ lived experiences of academic challenges and student success in Cambodian primary schools in Pailin Province, a context that reflects both urban and rural schooling realities.

Despite sustained policy reforms and near-universal access to primary schooling in Cambodia, persistent deficits in learning outcomes—particularly in foundational literacy and numeracy—remain critical concerns. National and international assessments continue to show that many primary school students complete early grades without mastering basic competencies, with challenges most pronounced in rural and resource-constrained settings (Benveniste et al., 2008; World Bank, 2018; UNESCO, 2022; Sam et al., 2025). In response, the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sport introduced the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) as a comprehensive framework to improve teaching quality, school leadership, accountability, and community participation (MoEYS, 2023). However, while the MPSS represents a significant policy commitment, there is limited empirical evidence on how these standards are enacted and experienced at the school level. In particular, the perspectives of teachers and parents—key actors

in students' daily learning environments—remain underexplored, leaving a gap in understanding how structural, institutional, and family-level factors interact to shape academic challenges and student success in practice.

The rationale for this study is grounded in the need for context-sensitive, qualitative evidence to inform the effective implementation of standards-based reforms such as MPSSs. Research on education quality in Cambodia has largely relied on system-level analyses and quantitative indicators, which, while valuable, provide limited insight into the lived realities of schools and families (Akyeampong & Fofack, 2019; UNESCO, 2022; Sam et al., 2025). Sociocultural theories emphasize that educational outcomes are shaped not only by formal policies but also by social relationships, local conditions, and everyday practices within schools and communities (Vygotsky, 1978). By examining teachers' and parents' lived experiences in Pailin Province, this study seeks to illuminate how MPSS-related reforms intersect with poverty, teacher workload, parental capacity, and community engagement. Generating such qualitative, ground-level evidence is essential for refining policy implementation, strengthening stakeholder collaboration, and ensuring that national education reforms translate into meaningful and equitable learning improvements for primary school students.

Materials and methods

Research Design

This study adopted a qualitative research design to explore teachers' and parents' lived experiences of academic challenges and student success within the context of MPSS implementation. A qualitative approach was appropriate for capturing participants' perceptions, meanings, and contextual realities that cannot be adequately understood through quantitative measures alone (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Merriam & Tisdell, 2016).

Study Site and Participants

The study was conducted in Pailin Province, Cambodia, which was selected for its active implementation of the MPSS and for its representation of both urban and rural school contexts. Purposive sampling was used to select participants with direct experience with primary education and the implementation of the MPSS. A total of 52 participants were included, comprising school principals, teachers, parents, and members of the school management committees of five public primary schools.

Data Collection

The data were collected through seven focus group discussions and eleven in-depth interviews via semistructured interview guides. The guides addressed teaching practices, professional development, school leadership, student learning experiences, parental involvement, and challenges related to MPSS implementation. All the sessions were conducted in Khmer, audio-recorded with participants' informed consent, and supplemented by field notes.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed via thematic analysis following established qualitative research procedures. All the interview and focus group transcripts were read repeatedly to achieve data familiarization, after which inductive coding was conducted to identify meaningful units of text. Codes were then compared, refined, and organized into broader categories and themes that captured patterned meanings across the dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2006, 2021). Throughout the analysis, emerging themes were systematically reviewed and refined to ensure coherence, internal consistency, and clear distinctions between themes. To increase the trustworthiness of the findings, data

triangulation across participant groups—including teachers, parents, school leaders, and school management committee members—was employed, allowing for the comparison of perspectives and strengthening the credibility of interpretations (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Poth, 2018).

Figure 1. Pailin Province Map

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Qualitative Participants (N = 52)

Participants	N	Age (Mean)	Age Range	Experience (Mean, years)	Experience Range (years)	Female (%)
School principals	5	43	42-45	12.0	5-23	40.0
Teachers	14	33	25-46	8.5	2-21	35.7
School management committee (SMC)	14	49	32-71	4.6	1-13	28.6
Parents	19	41	25-69	10.8	3-25	31.6
Total	52	41	25-71	8.7	1-25	32.7

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the qualitative participants (N = 52), including school principals, teachers, members of the school management committee (SMC), and parents. The table summarizes the participants’ age, years of experience, and gender composition across the four groups. The participants ranged in age from 25--71 years, with a mean age of 41 years. School management committee members constituted the oldest group, with an average age of 49 years, whereas teachers were the youngest, with a mean age of 33 years. The average age of the school principals was 43 years and that of the parents was 41 years, indicating a relatively balanced age distribution among the participant groups. The participants reported an average of 8.7 years of professional experience, with experience ranging from 1--25 years. School principals had the highest average level of experience (12.0 years), followed by parents (10.8 years) and teachers (8.5 years). School management committee members reported comparatively fewer years of experience, with an average of 4.6 years. Overall, approximately one-third of the participants were female (32.7%). Female representation varied across groups, with the highest proportion among school principals (40.0%) and the lowest among school management committee members (28.6%).

Results

The objective of this study is to investigate Teachers' and parents' lived experiences of academic challenges and success in Cambodian primary schools in Pailin Province. Teachers and parents identified a range of challenges that limited student learning, as well as factors that contributed to academic success. Their reflections pointed to the influence of student characteristics, family circumstances, teacher practices, and stakeholder support. Four major themes emerged from the analysis.

Theme 1: Structural and Socioeconomic Barriers to Student Learning

The findings indicate that student learning in Cambodian primary schools is profoundly shaped by structural and socioeconomic conditions that extend well beyond the classroom. The participants consistently emphasized poverty as a central barrier, not only because of material deprivation but also because of its cascading effects on attendance, concentration, and emotional well-being. Teachers and parents described how economic hardship compelled some children to engage in income-generating activities or household labor, particularly during agricultural seasons, leading to irregular attendance and learning disruptions. These patterns suggest that absenteeism is not merely an issue of parental negligence but also a survival strategy for families facing chronic financial insecurity. Consequently, students who missed instructional time often struggled to keep pace with lessons, reinforcing cycles of academic underachievement.

Family instability emerged as another significant constraint on learning. Participants highlighted that children from households affected by labor migration, separation, or domestic conflict were particularly vulnerable to academic difficulties. In such contexts, caregiving responsibilities are often fragmented, reducing consistent supervision of school attendance and learning at home. Teachers noted that these students frequently exhibited lower motivation, behavioral challenges, or difficulties sustaining attention in class, indicating the emotional and psychological toll of unstable home environments. This finding underscores that academic challenges are closely intertwined with students' socioemotional experiences, which directly influence their capacity to learn.

Limited parental education further compounded these challenges by constraining parents' ability to provide academic support at home. While many parents expressed strong aspirations for their children's success, low literacy levels and limited familiarity with school curricula limited their capacity to assist with homework or monitor their children's learning progress. As a result, learning support at home often takes indirect forms—such as encouraging attendance or urging children to listen to teachers—rather than direct instructional assistance. This highlights a critical mismatch between parental commitment and the cultural and educational capital available to students from less educated households, suggesting that students from such households face systemic disadvantages despite high parental motivation.

In addition, the participants reported that some students experienced learning difficulties related to intellectual disabilities, congenital health conditions, or exposure to domestic violence. Teachers described these students as requiring individualized attention, which was difficult to provide in overcrowded classrooms and without specialist support. The absence of trained special education personnel, school counselors, or referral mechanisms limits schools' capacity to respond effectively to diverse learning needs. Consequently, these students were at heightened risk of disengagement, grade repetition, or silent exclusion within mainstream classrooms. Together, these findings reveal that structural inequality, family vulnerability, and limited support services interact to shape students' academic trajectories, underscoring the need for education reforms integrated with social protection, health, and inclusive support systems rather than relying solely on classroom-based interventions. One teacher explained the impact of poverty on attendance and learning:

“Many students come to school irregularly because their families are poor. Some children have to help their parents work, especially during harvest time, so they miss lessons and fall behind.” (Teacher, FGD)

A parent similarly highlighted economic pressure and limited ability to support learning at home:

“I want my child to study well, but sometimes I need him to help me earn money. I cannot read well myself, so I don’t know how to help with homework.” (Parent, IDI)

The participants also reported that some students experienced learning difficulties related to intellectual disabilities, congenital health conditions, or exposure to domestic violence. Limited access to specialist support services further constrains these students’ sustained academic engagement.

A school principal noted:

“Some students have health or learning problems, but we do not have specialists or support teachers. The classroom teacher has to manage alone, which is very difficult.” (Principal, IDI)

Theme 2: Institutional and Pedagogical Constraints in Teaching Practice

Teachers described heavy workloads, large class sizes, and insufficient instructional resources as barriers to effective teaching. Limited access to teaching aids, technology, and professional development constrains their ability to implement learner-centered approaches promoted under MPSS. Principals emphasized the difficulty of balancing administrative responsibilities with instructional leadership, particularly in schools facing staff shortages. The findings reveal that institutional and pedagogical constraints significantly shaped teachers’ instructional practices and limited the effective implementation of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS). Teachers consistently described heavy workloads and large class sizes as major obstacles to providing individualized support and using interactive, learner-centered approaches. Managing classrooms with diverse learning needs requires substantial time and emotional labor, which limits the capacity for differentiated instruction or formative assessment. As a result, teachers often rely on whole-class, textbook-centered methods, not out of resistance to reform but rather as a pragmatic response to institutional pressures and time constraints.

Insufficient instructional resources further constrain pedagogical innovation. Teachers reported limited access to teaching aids, supplementary learning materials, and basic technology, which restricted opportunities to engage students through hands-on activities, visual support, or differentiated tasks. These resource limitations disproportionately affect students with learning difficulties, who require alternative explanations or additional practices. While MPSS promotes active learning and competency-based instruction, the findings suggest a misalignment between policy expectations and material conditions in schools. Teachers’ accounts indicate that pedagogical reform cannot be sustained without parallel investment in classroom resources that support diverse teaching strategies.

Professional development opportunities were also perceived as inadequate for addressing classroom realities. Although teachers acknowledged the importance of MPSS training, many reported that workshops were short, infrequent, or overly theoretical, with limited opportunities for practice, mentoring, or follow-up support. This limited the transfer of new knowledge to daily teaching. Teachers emphasized that without ongoing coaching or peer learning, it was difficult to adapt MPSS principles to large, mixed-ability classrooms. These findings highlight that capacity building must move beyond one-off training sessions toward continuous, school-based professional learning that responds to teachers’ contextual challenges.

Principals’ narratives further illuminate institutional constraints at the leadership level. Many principals described the challenge of balancing administrative compliance, reporting requirements,

and teaching responsibilities, particularly in schools experiencing staff shortages. These competing demands reduce the time for classroom observation, instructional feedback, and teacher mentoring—key components of effective instructional leadership. Consequently, leadership support for pedagogical improvement was often limited, not because of a lack of commitment but rather because of structural and workload pressures. Taken together, these findings suggest that institutional conditions—staffing, resources, and leadership capacity—play a decisive role in shaping classroom practice. Without addressing these systemic constraints, the transformative potential of the MPSS is likely to remain constrained, reinforcing the need for reforms that simultaneously strengthen teaching conditions, leadership support, and institutional capacity.

One teacher reflected on classroom conditions:

“I teach many students in one class, and there are not enough materials. It is difficult to use new teaching methods when we only have textbooks.” (Teacher, FGD)

Another teacher emphasized limited professional development opportunities:

“Training is important, but sometimes it is short or not related to our real classroom problems. Without enough practice, it is hard to apply the MPSS properly.” (Teacher, IDI)

Principals emphasized the difficulty of balancing administrative responsibilities with instructional leadership, particularly in schools facing staff shortages.

A principal explained:

“I am both a principal and a teacher. I have many reports and meetings, so I don’t always have time to observe classes or support teachers as I should.” (Principal, IDI)

Theme 3: Parental Engagement as Both a Constraint and a Resource

Although parental involvement was often inconsistent, the participants emphasized that many parents held strong aspirations for their children’s education. Parents supported learning through informal practices such as monitoring attendance, communicating with teachers via notebooks, and encouraging children at home. However, low literacy levels and economic pressures limit parents’ capacity to engage more actively in school-based activities. The findings illustrate that parental engagement in Cambodian primary schools is complex and shaped by parents’ socioeconomic realities rather than by a lack of interest in their children’s education. The participants consistently emphasized that many parents held strong aspirations for their children’s academic success and viewed education as a pathway to improved life opportunities. These aspirations were reflected in parents’ efforts to ensure regular school attendance, encourage children to listen to teachers, and express concern about academic progress. Such forms of engagement, although informal, play an important motivational role in sustaining students’ commitment to learning and reinforcing the value of schooling within the household.

Parents’ support for learning was most evident through low-cost, practical strategies that aligned with their daily routines and capacities. Monitoring attendance, checking communication notebooks, and maintaining contact with teachers allowed parents to stay informed about their children’s progress despite limited formal education. Teachers acknowledged that these practices, while modest, helped students feel supported and accountable, particularly when parents followed up on teacher feedback at home. This finding suggests that parental engagement should not be narrowly defined by visible participation in school activities but rather understood as a continuum of practices that reflect families’ social and cultural contexts.

Moreover, low literacy levels significantly constrain parents’ ability to provide direct academic support, such as assisting with homework or reinforcing lesson content at home. Many parents reported feeling inadequate or embarrassed about their limited education, which reduced their

confidence in their ability to engage more actively with teachers or school leadership. Economic pressures further compound these constraints, as long working hours, seasonal labor demands, and job insecurity limit parents' ability to attend school meetings or participate in school-based initiatives. As a result, parental involvement often appears inconsistent from the school's perspective, even though parents remain emotionally invested in their children's education.

These findings highlight a mismatch between school expectations of parental involvement and the lived realities of families in low-income contexts. While schools often emphasize attendance at meetings or participation in formal activities, parents' circumstances necessitate more flexible and informal forms of engagement. This tension suggests that parental involvement policies embedded within MPSS may inadvertently privilege families with greater educational and economic resources. To harness parental engagement as a meaningful resource, schools must adopt inclusive, context-sensitive approaches that validate informal support practices and create accessible communication channels. Recognizing parents as partners—despite structural limitations—can strengthen trust, enhance home-school relationships, and contribute to more equitable learning outcomes for students.

A parent expressed strong educational aspirations despite constraints:

"I did not study much, but I want my child to have a better future. I always tell my child to listen to the teacher and go to school every day." (Parent, FGD)

A teacher highlighted informal but meaningful parental support:

"Some parents cannot help with homework, but they check the notebook and talk with us. This communication helps the child feel supported." (Teacher, IDI)

At the same time, parents acknowledged barriers to deeper engagement:

"Sometimes the school calls meetings, but I cannot attend because I have to work. I want to help, but I don't have much time." (Parent, IDI)

Theme 4: Conditions Supporting Student Academic Success

Student success was associated with regular attendance, teacher encouragement, additional academic support, and effective communication between schools and families. The participants highlighted that collaboration among teachers, principals, parents, and community members was essential for monitoring student progress and addressing learning difficulties. The findings indicate that student academic success in Cambodian primary schools is closely linked to a set of interrelated relational, instructional, and organizational conditions rather than to any single factor. Regular school attendance emerged as a foundational condition for learning, as consistent exposure to instruction enabled students to build cumulative knowledge and maintain engagement with classroom routines. Teachers emphasized that students who attended school regularly were better able to follow lesson sequences, participate actively, and develop confidence in their abilities. In contrast, irregular attendance disrupted learning continuity and often resulted in students falling behind, highlighting attendance as both an outcome of supportive conditions and a prerequisite for academic success.

Teacher encouragement played a central role in sustaining student motivation and engagement, particularly for learners facing socioeconomic or learning-related challenges. The participants described how positive feedback, praise, and emotional support helped students develop confidence and persistence, even when academic progress was slow. This encouragement fostered a sense of belonging and safety within the classroom, enabling students to take risks in learning and remain engaged despite difficulties. Teachers' narratives suggest that affective dimensions of

teaching—often undervalued in policy frameworks—were critical in promoting resilience and sustained effort among students.

Additional academic support, including remedial instruction and targeted assistance for struggling learners, was also identified as a key contributor to student success. Teachers noted that students who received extra guidance—either during or after regular class time—were more likely to overcome learning gaps and improve performance. However, the provision of such support often depends on teachers’ individual initiative rather than on structured school-wide systems. This finding indicates that while compensatory practices were effective, their sustainability and reach remained uneven, underscoring the need for institutionalized support mechanisms within schools.

Effective communication and collaboration among teachers, principals, parents, and community members further strengthened the conditions for student success. The participants emphasized that regular information sharing enabled early identification of learning difficulties and facilitated coordinated responses across home and school environments. Communication tools, such as notebooks and informal meetings, help align expectations and reinforce learning support at home. Community involvement, including support from school management committees, enhanced collective responsibility for student outcomes and reinforced accountability. Together, these findings demonstrate that student success is most likely when learning is supported through collaborative, trust-based relationships that extend beyond the classroom, suggesting that MPSS implementation should prioritize relational coordination and shared ownership alongside instructional standards.

A teacher emphasized the role of encouragement:

“When students come to school every day and receive encouragement, they improve. Even small praise makes them more confident.” (Teacher, FGD)

A parent described how communication with teachers supported learning:

“When the teacher writes in the communication book, I know how my child is doing. I remind my child to study more when there is a problem.” (Parent, IDI)

A school management committee member stressed collective responsibility:

“Student success improves when the school, parents, and community work together. We cannot leave education only to teachers.” (SMC member, FGD)

Table 2. Summary of Themes and Exemplar Participant Quotations

Theme	Description	Exemplar Quotations
Theme 1: Structural and Socioeconomic Barriers to Student Learning	Student learning is constrained by poverty, family instability, limited parental education, health conditions, and lack of specialist support. These factors contribute to absenteeism, reduced study time, and learning difficulties.	<p><i>“Many students come to school irregularly because their families are poor. Some children have to help their parents work, so they miss lessons and fall behind.”</i> (Teacher, FGD)</p> <p><i>“I want my child to study well, but sometimes I need him to help me earn money. I cannot read well myself, so I don’t know how to help with homework.”</i> (Parent, IDI)</p>
Theme 2: Institutional and Pedagogical Constraints in Teaching Practice	Teachers face heavy workloads, large class sizes, limited resources, and insufficient professional development, which restrict effective implementation of MPSS and learner-centered instruction.	<i>“I teach many students in one class, and there are not enough materials. It is difficult to use new teaching methods when we only have textbooks.”</i>

		(Teacher, FGD) "I am both a principal and a teacher. I have many reports and meetings, so I don't always have time to support teachers in the classroom." (Principal, IDI)
Theme 3: Parental Engagement as Both a Constraint and a Resource	Parents value education and provide informal support, but low literacy levels, work demands, and economic pressures limit consistent participation in school activities.	"I did not study much, but I want my child to have a better future. I always tell my child to go to school and listen to the teacher." (Parent, FGD) "Some parents cannot help with homework, but they check the notebook and communicate with us. This support is important for students." (Teacher, IDI)
Theme 4: Conditions Supporting Student Academic Success	Student success is supported by regular attendance, teacher encouragement, additional academic support, effective communication, and collaboration among schools, families, and communities.	"When students attend regularly and receive encouragement, their learning improves. Even small praise makes them more confident." (Teacher, FGD) "Student success improves when the school, parents, and community work together. Education is a shared responsibility." (SMC member, FGD)

Discussion

These findings align with sociocultural perspectives on learning, which emphasize that academic development is socially mediated through interaction, relationships, and shared cultural practices (Vygotsky, 1978). Teachers' and parents' narratives demonstrate that learning is not solely a classroom process but is deeply influenced by family circumstances, school leadership, and community engagement. Although parents in low-income and rural contexts face significant constraints, their aspirations and informal support practices play a meaningful role in sustaining student motivation. These findings are consistent with international evidence showing that parental expectations and encouragement are stronger predictors of academic achievement than direct homework assistance is (Jeynes, 2012). However, inconsistent engagement and limited leadership capacity constrain the effectiveness of MPSS implementation.

The results suggest that standard-based reforms such as the MPSS must be accompanied by flexible, context-sensitive strategies that support teachers, strengthen leadership capacity, and accommodate families' lived realities. Without addressing structural constraints such as poverty, resource shortages, and workload pressures, policy reforms have a limited impact on classroom practice and student learning.

Theme 1: Structural and Socioeconomic Barriers to Student Learning

The findings related to structural and socioeconomic barriers reinforce sociocultural and ecological perspectives on learning, which emphasize that children's academic development is shaped by broader social, economic, and familial contexts (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Vygotsky, 1978). Teachers' and parents' accounts in this study illustrate how poverty, family instability, health issues, and limited parental education constrained regular attendance, concentration, and sustained engagement in learning. These findings are consistent with prior research in Cambodia and other

low- and middle-income countries, which shows that economic hardship and household vulnerability are strongly associated with absenteeism, early-grade learning gaps, and an increased risk of dropout (Benveniste et al., 2008; World Bank, 2018). The lack of access to specialist services for children with learning difficulties further exacerbated inequities, placing additional strain on classroom teachers. These conditions highlight that academic challenges cannot be addressed solely through pedagogical reform but require multisectoral responses that address child well-being, health, and household poverty. Without mitigating these structural constraints, efforts to improve learning outcomes through school-level standards such as MPSS may have a limited and uneven impact.

Theme 2: Institutional and Pedagogical Constraints in Teaching Practice

The institutional and pedagogical constraints identified in this study underscore the critical role of teacher working conditions and leadership capacity in shaping instructional quality. Teachers' reports of heavy workloads, large class sizes, limited teaching materials, and insufficient professional development echo broader evidence that such conditions undermine the effective implementation of learner-centered reforms in developing education systems (Akyeampong et al., 2013; UNESCO, 2022). Principals' difficulties in balancing administrative duties with instructional leadership further constrained opportunities for classroom support and professional learning. Research suggests that school leadership focused on instructional improvement is a key driver of teacher effectiveness and student learning, particularly in resource-constrained contexts (Hallinger & Heck, 2010; Leithwood et al., 2020). While the MPSS articulates expectations for quality teaching and leadership, the findings indicate that insufficient time, training, and resources limit schools' capacity to translate policy standards into everyday practice. This reinforces the need for systemic support mechanisms—rather than compliance-oriented accountability alone—to enable teachers and school leaders to enact reforms meaningfully.

Theme 3: Parental Engagement as Both a Constraint and a Resource

The findings regarding parental engagement reveal a nuanced picture in which parents' strong educational aspirations coexist with significant practical constraints. Despite low literacy levels and demanding work conditions, many parents supported learning through encouragement, monitoring attendance, and communication with teachers. This aligns with international evidence showing that parental expectations, aspirations, and emotional support are consistently associated with higher student achievement, even when parents are unable to provide direct academic assistance (Jeynes, 2012; Hill & Tyson, 2009). However, inconsistent participation in school activities due to economic pressures limits deeper engagement, reflecting patterns observed in rural and low-income settings globally (UNESCO, 2022). These findings suggest that traditional models of parental involvement may inadequately capture meaningful forms of engagement practiced by marginalized families. For MPSS implementation to be inclusive and effective, schools must adopt flexible, culturally responsive approaches that value informal parental support and reduce participation barriers rather than relying solely on school-based meetings or formal activities.

Theme 4: Conditions Supporting Student Academic Success

Conditions associated with student academic success in this study—regular attendance, teacher encouragement, additional learning support, and effective home–school communication—highlight the importance of relational and motivational factors in early learning. Teachers' emphasis on encouragement and positive feedback provides evidence that supportive teacher–student relationships enhance engagement, self-efficacy, and academic outcomes, particularly for students facing adversity (Hattie, 2009; Wentzel, 2012). Similarly, parents' use of communication tools to monitor progress aligns with research demonstrating that consistent home–school communication supports early identification of learning difficulties and promotes shared responsibility for student

success (Epstein, 2018). The findings also underscore that academic success is most sustainable when schools, families, and communities collaborate, reinforcing sociocultural views of learning as a collective endeavor (Vygotsky, 1978). These insights suggest that MPSS implementation should prioritize relational practices and collaborative structures alongside technical standards, ensuring that reforms strengthen the social foundations of learning and instructional quality.

Conclusion

This study explored teachers' and parents' lived experiences with academic challenges and student success in Cambodian primary schools within the context of MPSS implementation in Pailin Province. The findings reveal that student learning is shaped by a complex interaction of socioeconomic conditions, teacher capacity, leadership support, and parental engagement. While the MPSS provides an important framework for improving school quality, its effectiveness depends on sustained teacher support, leadership development, and inclusive, context-sensitive approaches to parental participation. Addressing structural constraints is essential for translating policy reforms into meaningful and equitable learning outcomes. The study contributes qualitative evidence to education reform discourse in Cambodia and offers practical insights for strengthening primary education in similar resource-constrained settings.

Recommendations for Policymakers and Education Authorities

National and provincial education authorities should prioritize strengthening the implementation of the Model Primary School Standards (MPSS) through sustained investment in teacher support, leadership development, and school resources. Targeted professional development programs are needed to reduce teacher workload pressures and enhance pedagogical capacity, particularly in rural and resource-constrained contexts such as Pailin Province. Regular, needs-based training aligned with classroom realities—especially learner-centered instruction, inclusive education, and formative assessment—would support teachers in meeting MPSS expectations. In addition, education authorities should ensure that school principals receive structured leadership training focused on instructional supervision, school management, and stakeholder coordination. Strengthening monitoring and support mechanisms at the district and provincial levels, rather than relying solely on compliance-based inspections, may improve accountability while fostering professional growth. Policymakers should also consider flexible resource allocation models that address disparities among schools, including access to teaching materials, basic technology, and student support services, to ensure that MPSS implementation contributes meaningfully to improved learning outcomes.

Recommendations for School Leaders and Teachers

School leaders and teachers play a central role in translating education policies into effective classroom practices. Principals are encouraged to promote collaborative school cultures that support shared problem solving, peer learning, and reflective teaching practices. Establishing regular professional learning communities within schools may help teachers exchange strategies for addressing student learning difficulties, managing large classes, and engaging parents more effectively. Teachers should support the adoption of flexible and inclusive instructional approaches that accommodate diverse student needs, including those affected by poverty, health challenges, or learning difficulties. Given the constraints identified in this study, schools may benefit from prioritizing low-cost, high-impact strategies, such as structured remedial support, consistent student monitoring, and the effective use of parent–teacher communication tools. Strengthening principals' instructional leadership—particularly through regular classroom observation and constructive feedback—can further enhance teaching quality and support sustained professional development.

Recommendations for Parents, Communities, and Other Stakeholders

Parents, communities, and school management committees are essential partners in supporting student learning and school development. Efforts should be made to promote inclusive and realistic models of parental engagement that acknowledge families' economic constraints and literacy levels. Schools can facilitate this by providing clear, accessible guidance on how parents can support learning at home, even though simple practices such as monitoring attendance, encouraging study habits, and maintaining communication with teachers. Community awareness programs highlighting the long-term value of education may help strengthen shared responsibility for student success. Collaboration among schools, local authorities, and community organizations could also support initiatives to address barriers such as absenteeism, child labor, and student well-being. By fostering trust-based partnerships and open communication, stakeholders can create supportive learning environments that reinforce students' motivation and academic success, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness and sustainability of MPSS implementation.

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Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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